

Collocation and colligation analysis of the verb “wax”

1. Introduction

This paper aims to characterize the units of meaning of the verb “wax” in terms of its collocation, colligation, semantic preference, and semantic prosody, as well as variation. The framework “units of meaning” is based on Sinclair’s article¹. The data is collected from the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA). The units of meaning found in the corpus will be compared with the meanings provided by Collins dictionary² which gives meanings of the verb “wax” as follow:

- A. to coat, polish, etc, with wax
- B. to remove (body hair) by means of a wax treatment
- C. to become larger, more powerful, etc
- D. (of the moon) to increase in the extent of its illuminated portion before the full moon
- E. to speak or express oneself
- F. to grow or become

2. Methods

The regular expression used is [wax].[v*]. In the collocation analysis, the regular expression will be used in the **Collocates** tab with the -3 and +3 adjacent words parameter. In the colligation analysis, the same regular expression will be used in the **KWIC** tab with N+1 and N+2 positions.

3. Results

3.1. Collocation Analysis

Collocation analysis yields a preposition “about” as the most frequent collocate with the frequency of 411 hits followed by an adjective “poetic” (207 hits). The two collocates are related semantically with the **meaning E**, to speak or express oneself; however, the meaning in the corpus is more general, which is to speak or express, not necessarily about oneself or even a person as in the example: *Angelinos sometimes like to wax poetic about how the dusty, hot winds can change people.* “**Wax poetic about,**” thus, is a unit of meaning that means to become increasingly verbose about something. Other similar units of meaning are “**wax nostalgic**”, “**wax lyrical**”, “**wax philosophical**”, and “**wax eloquent**”. The third place is a verb “waned” with 104 hits, which belongs to the **meaning C and D** same as its present form “wane”. “**Wax and wane**” in this sense covers both literal and

¹ Sinclair, John. 2004[1996]. The search for units of meaning. *Textus* 9(1). 75–106. Reprinted in *Trust the text: Language, corpus and discourse*, 24–48. London: Routledge.

² <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/wax>

metaphorical meanings of enlargement and diminution. Therefore, it is found to co-occur with not only “moon” but also other abstract and material nouns like influence, freedom, companies and immigrants. Another interesting unit of meaning is found with the occurrence of itself “wax” as in the “**Wax on. Wax off.**” construction as introduced in an American film. According to the context in the film, “Wax on. Wax off.”, means repetitive practice makes perfect. This meaning is not indicated in the Collins dictionary. Therefore, this demonstrates the **variation** of the usage originated from a particular context and became generalized and more popular later.

3.2. Colligation Analysis

Performing a colligation analysis over the concordance of 200 randomly selected lines at N+1 and N+2 levels each, the findings are as follow:

3.2.1. N+1

In this layer, the majority of the words that occur right after the verb “wax” are **adjectives** in the meaning E, to speak or express at the rate of 19% comprising, for example, nostalgic, poetic, eloquent, lyrical, philosophical. Those adjectives modifying the manner of waxing or speaking demonstrate a clear **semantic preference related to the description of manner**.

3.2.2. N+2

At this level, the predominant constructions are “**wax+adj.+prep.**” at 15%; for instance, “wax warmly about”, “wax Socratic in”, and “wax moralistic on” followed by “wax and wane” in the meaning C and D at 11.5%. In addition, **a variety of materials being waxed** as in the meaning A has emerged as a new **variation** at 12.5%, such as your lips, their cars, the floors, and the hallways. Setting aside “wax and wane” with its own ungeneralizable meaning, a strong **semantic prosody of objects** is apparent. Both an object of preposition, wax about or on someone or some topic, and an object of verb, wax something, can be found even more frequently in the level N+2 and beyond.

4. Summary and Discussion

Overall, based on collocation and colligation analysis, the verb “wax” has 2 main meanings: “speak” and “coat or polish” while a semantic preference related to “the description of manner” is detected in N+1 and a variation “material being waxed” in N+2. A semantic prosody of objects is found in N+2 and beyond. In the first meaning, language users tend to modify it with an adjective to describe the manner, and in both meanings, speakers often put an object either a person or a topic in the meaning “speak” or a material in the meaning “coat or polish”. It would be interesting to explore a semantic feature and a semantic prosody in other levels like N-1 and N-2 to see if there are additional variations.

Appendix 1

N+1			
Line	Left	Middle	Right
1	would have protected it ! # I have a question about	waxing	a dining room table vs poly . I am converting a dresser
2	high school student is required to take . Throughout Heinlein	waxes	about social mores and the human condition -- the things that
3	the Wexner , Mr. Bradford appeared restless . Was all this	waxing	about torn-down posters reminding him of those dreaded
4	the words " bush " and Clinton , meaning gardening and	waxing	ads were being blocked . Martinez argued on Twitter that
5	other vertical or shaded surfaces . And do n't forget to	wax	all exterior metal hardware , Reisert reminded , since most
6	, vice president of supply management for United Technologies ,	waxes	almost Meakemesque on the subject . " This FreeMarkets auction
7	full moon : they grew but could not last . They	waxed	and waned without the real orbit changing . It should not have
8	decimated first echelon and committing his second . The battle	waxed	and waned through the day . Abrash had planned another all-out
9	hand pops back up to my brow . # This urge	waxed	and waned like a primal tide throughout high school . I hid
10	sporadic recycling efforts and an environmental dub that	waxed	and waned in size like a seasonal cow pond . The other
11	experiences . According to my colleagues , her symptoms	waxed	and waned in fairly close correlation to her level of valproic
12	repression . # Insurgent resistance to military rule	waxed	and waned in two long cycles . The first peaked around 1970
13	since the 1800s . # " The popularity of gnomes has	waxed	and waned over the past 150 years , " says Margaret Egleton
14	for Jordan 's inter-Arab relations , which have historically	waxed	and waned with the currents of the time . Immediately after the
15	since the middle of the nineteenth century . The issue has	waxed	and waned through the years , but it has always been there
16	be grouped together in a single agency . This idea has	waxed	and waned with rhythmic regularity . At present , the idea is
17	the pact represents a major victory in a campaign that has	waxed	and waned since the first atomic bombs were dropped at the end
18	with the head of Tifwan , Ba . This conflict has	waxed	and waned over a very long time . A Quarterly Report for
19	# The West 's love-hate affair with oil shale has been	waxing	and waning for centuries . Legends are told of American Indians
20	Her Orange County business offered services such as facials ,	waxing	and wrinkle treatments . # A voicemail recording at her
21	track of which days to sow aboveground or root crops in	waxing	and waning phases , and which were the best days to fertilize
22	: Well , this is a guy who certainly would be	waxing	and nostalgic and maybe even melancholy for an election he
23	and arms . What can we do to help ? Leg	waxing	and laser treatments involve more pain than I want her to submit
24	emerge on plants attacked by parasites , and a sense of	waxing	and waning violence permeated the 15-minute work . The opening
25	the Earth 's orbit around the Sun . These changes forced	waxing	and waning of ice sheets accompanied by global changes in sea
26	strategies , as social concerns with environmental issues	wax	and wane over time. (n21) Ozone depletion hit the public
27	say , " Heji-ubifen and Fenjiubihe , " meaning " Empires	wax	and wane , as well as states cleave asunder and coalesce ,
28	use century old handwritten records . Do n't use conditions that	wax	and wane , or get better with time . Use a non-self-limiting
29	. I assume from your post that you know how to	wax	and are not looking for advice on that . If not ,
30	in her . The inquiry was complete . She did indeed	wax	and was predictably bourgeois . I wondered about India , but the
31	on your newfound energy . " Your motivation will naturally	wax	and wane , " says Slayton . " When you 're in
32	# (V.O.) The light of the Evenstar does not	wax	and wane . It is mine to give to whom I will
33	can you tiink of anything lovelier than watching Sister Moon	wax	and wane ? When my children ask why their parents ' lives

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34	season , but as with November 's rut its strength can	wax	and wane depending on the weather , the buck-to-doe ratio of the
35	For example , a tally of the number of writing tasks	Wax	assigned -- tasks that included individual essays ,
36	in all .) Asparagus Snap peas Green beans Fava beans	Wax	beans Peas Bok choy Swiss chard (leaves and stems cooked
37	caps , brushed clean # 15 to 20 string beans or	wax	beans , stringed , trimmed # 1 package (12 ounces)
38	main ideological tenets . It 's a massive issue they can	wax	BS at to pretend they care for " foreigners " etc .
39	chalky streaks . Vinegar in the formula dissolves grease and	wax	buildup. \$3.79/22 oz. 800.335.3267 ; ecos.com Homemade Option
40	. But electric candles in sconces line the walls , and	wax	candles cover the tables , their wicks sputtering when Jesmyn
41	Surprisingly , there 's minimal evidence that bras help . Can	waxing	cause STDs ? It 's unlikely , but cut your odds by
42	roaming about with certificates of corruption ! The love of God	waxes	cold in her fertile hearts , Occupied with cruel wickedness and
43	Thomas Hart Benton , " Dancer , " graphite pencil and	wax	crayon on paper (1930) . # Thomas Hart Benton ,
44	moon , and last quarter are the four primary phases .	Waxing	crescent , waxing gibbous , waning gibbous , and waning crescent
45	of recording images and sound , such as nitrate film and	wax	cylinders , to the more contemporary formats of videotape and
46	Garcia -- from early Dead to JGB . No use in	waxing	cynical , it 's Jerry Week and all the GD devotees are
47	? Whoa ! ' Hah , voodoo dolls ! ' These	wax	dolls do come in handy . ' So that 's where the
48	professors of English study Melville or Pynchon . " # Thompson	waxes	eloquent when he talks about the good that serious study of
49	Cliff Gustafson and Bibb Falk . These days , Garrido is	waxing	eloquent as a Longhorn Network/ESPN analyst at the regional
50	that , tellingly , seems reminiscent of the young Wordsworth	waxing	eloquent about the consolations of Nature) that art " guides and
51	m trying to remember what the question was before I started	waxing	eloquent . 8th REPORTER : The outcome , dependent upon this case
52	apathy or that I do n't care about these things I	wax	eloquent about . Quite the opposite really . I do care about
53	share resources with one another and have been known to	wax	eloquent on a teaching approach that succeeded wildly or failed
54	" Ah , yes . Funny how liberals suddenly come to	wax	enthusiastic about Edmund Burke when they are in power , and when
55	Let me get into this now because I want to just	wax	enthusiastic all over the place . SIMON : Please . PINKWATER
56	into a true classic . # Shower Power Award # To	wax	esoteric , the best shower-room water pressure among our Top 100
57	any time , about any character or situation . The narrator	waxes	especially ironic when he introduces a character for the first
58	a full head of hair ! ? How can a person	wax	euphoric over so many delicious foodstuffs and not be obese ?
59	Americans wearied of the struggle and quit , leaving Japan to	wax	fat on its conquests and to reign as master of East Asia
60	, included items such as rags , pens , rosaries ,	wax	figurines , and written notes.33 # It is all too easy to
61	that has defects . There are several different techniques . #	Wax	fill-in sticks # Good for scratches , small dings , dents or
62	microscope slide , using tiny glass beads for the bumps and	wax	for the troughs . For all nature 's sophistication , many of
63	Mexican-American (and here 's a hint : I want to	wax	Frida Kahlo 's furry caterpillar unibrow and I 'm thoroughly
64	in a great , wondrous necklace . Okay , before you	wax	geriatric , let me just cut to the chase . Henry is
65	It flares it does-the civil strife-it wanes to a fingernail and	waxes	gibbous , it ravages the countryside , while back in Londinium
66	Cade had taught her the moon phases like incantatory phrases .	Waxing	gibbous . Full . Waning gibbous . Half moon . Waning crescent
67	access , my faded blue JanSport overflowing with books . Moon	waxing	gibbous . Clouds .20 , thin , dark and passing over the
68	last quarter are the four primary phases . Waxing crescent ,	waxing	gibbous , waning gibbous , and waning crescent are the
69	, or cream added) as the only fluid that I	wax	going to drink the entire time . I would not change my
70	boy ! - LANI : Stop it ! Come on ,	wax	head ! - Hey ! Hey ! - LANI : Stop it

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71	glance , he seemed like any 16-year-old . While Akram was	waxing	his beloved Ford Mustang , two teenage girls shyly approached
72	as exorcists who performed the ritual by destroying a clay or	wax	image of a demon meant to destroy the attached spirit. iii
73	government . Even as late as 1989 , N.G.L. Hammond could	wax	in his The Macedonian State , " Alexander 's ideas on race
74	them to indulge their elitism behind a humanitarian facade :	waxing	indignant about how they were only trying to feed the poor and
75	autonomous unit for mid-mall snacking . If you 're gon na	wax	intellectual about the subject-- Holy shit ! - Wait here . -
76	shrink any more than is necessary . Nor does Clinton often	wax	judgmental . He is presumably aware that politicians who live in
77	coming here and you always had the best Halloween candy .	Wax	lips and candy corn . I remember my windows being soaped every
78	with stories about his days as a feminist icon , and	waxed	lyrical about fatherhood and male sacrifice . He also invited
79	Henry James , who in his 1907 book The American Scene	waxed	lyrical on the city 's " shy sweetness " and simple charms-
80	an opportunist , effete , pretentious and for a guy who	waxed	lyrical about ' Rock of Ages ' and ' MIB III '
81	my 34 years covering the Shaw Festival , I have often	waxed	lyrical about this pretty little town . Just about five hours
82	evaporate from the bottoms of your skis before waxing .	Wax	manufacturers have made waxing quick and easy by producing
83	of the hive entrance , the bees use the propolis and	wax	mixture as a caulking compound to plaster up any unwanted holes
84	Muslims and took back the holy land . # Americans who	wax	moralistic about Israel 's " unjust " possession of its land
85	. It is my position that the USA 's decision to	wax	moralistic on this point was what got us committed to our present
86	sick , in body or spirit ; when their case is	waxing	more and more desperate every day ; when all hope of recovery
87	and local public schools . By integrating a social studies	wax	museum into the teacher education curriculum , professors
88	http : **26;3246;TOOLONG . # One activity , the social studies	wax	museum , helped make social studies interesting for the
89	ways to interest them in the subject . A social studies	wax	museum is one way to bring state or national historical
90	it . Check this out . Is that Burt Reynolds ?	Wax	Museum . - What is this ? - That is a lot
91	has four wax figure s of herself at Madame Tussaud s	Wax	Museums in Washington D.C. , Vienna , Berlin , and London .
92	too . Yeah , right . I shave my arms and	wax	my upper lip , okay ? - You 're saying that to
93	by a lunch of iced tea and laxatives . Then I	wax	my arms , legs and eyebrows ... while power-lifting the couch to
94	get more excited over other people 's triumphs than my own	wax	my car , slowly , with a bikini . # Article copyright
95	not like I know what to do . Maybe I should	wax	my chest in case the milk comes . Take a deep breath
96	exciting ideas . Then there are a minority of individuals who	wax	negative . As one who used to wallow in this mud I
97	Serling 's " Twilight Zone , " this cantankerous producer almost	waxes	nostalgic . " Now there 's someone who did well without doing
98	novel and still emergent phenomenon . Kathryn Jean Lopez still	waxes	nostalgic for the days of " shotgun marriages " at National
99	cycle . Tonight he hit for the bicycle . " #	Waxing	nostalgic # A wax figure of the Knicks ' Carmelo Anthony was
100	PAULA ABDUL . This year 's model saw the Laker Girl	waxing	nostalgic about a sweeter , more innocent period in our past .
101	(left vs. right) . Some cold warriors are already	waxing	nostalgic for the good old days when they knew where they were
102	A DAY from trip 's end . Already , I 'm	waxing	nostalgic , trying to stretch and deepen every moment . I grab
103	! " # Some of us , perhaps , might still	wax	nostalgic for pre-air-conditioned America . For real life . For
104	still writing to complain about conditions where they are , to	wax	nostalgic about how things must be back home , to reminisce and
105	important . Wax on , wax off . Wax on ,	wax	off . RALPH-MACCHIO-COBR : Hey , where did these cars come from
106	Borrow from Elvis next time see him . Wax on ,	wax	off . Very good , Julie-san . Miss spot . This called
107	SERENDIPITY # How so ? # METATRON # Wax on ,	wax	off . (points OC) The Woman rolls up Her sleeves
108	JOE-DOOLEY# And it feels like hot fudge . MO ROCCA :	Wax	off . DANIELLE-ZANFARDIN# Turn to the side . JOE-DOOLEY# No

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109	branch thereof will not cease.Though the root thereof	wax	old in theearth , and the stock thereof die in the ground
110	heavens shall vanish away like smoke , and the earth shall	wax	old like a garment , and they that dwell therein shall die
111	to your apartment . " # Just as the presenters began	waxing	on about Kevin Day unfortunate fall to the pressures of being a
112	. Speaking of , how bout that Opening Reading I was	waxing	on earlier . You know who else was stellar ? Leigh Stein
113	wanted quick little snippets with links to resources . I was	waxing	on about philosophical things that factor into coverage and
114	yet , he kinda knows what he 's talking about .	Wax	on , wax off type of [Bleep] . Italian style . High
115	. All is being taken care of . How so ?	Wax	on , wax off . How did I -- She can rebuild
116	kind of Karate Kid , Mr . Miyagi groove thing ?	Wax	on , wax off . You 'll find references to modern culture
117	n't care and do bad work . Stay with tweezing ,	waxing	or lotions instead . # Electrologists try to discourage
118	? How are you ? Do you have relatives ? You	waxing	or shave ? You hermaphrodite ? What are you doing ? You
119	hairs at a time , like those you 've missed from	waxing	or shaving . Tweezing does sting a little , but the pain
120	should be the one about which we know least -- always	waxing	or waning , and now curved into the horns of a sickle
121	. We know very little about the origins of wiping and	waxing	or how rapidly these behaviors might evolve . Nevertheless ,
122	mariachis , see the guitarist shaking glass , wood , and	wax	out of his hair . She could see the people who stood
123	butter cup finely chopped , lightly salted roasted peanuts	Wax	paper 1 . Microwave first 3 ingrethents in a medium-size
124	: # Vegetable oil or nonstick cooking spray and parchment or	wax	paper # 3/4 cup chopped pitted dates # 1/2 cup pecan halves
125	slow down the process . # store with plastic wrap or	wax	paper pressed down to the surface of the guac to eliminate air
126	PG Tested So easy ! They 'll disappear in minutes .	Wax	paper 10 wooden picks 10 large marshmallows cup graham cracker
127	: Baby Jesuses in walnut shells , clothespin soldiers ,	wax	paper stars . # " Ed called , " Aunt Jean said
128	with parchment paper . On a separate sheet of parchment or	wax	paper , place half the dough . Form a long log ,
129	DIGGINS (United States) -Indigo Bark Group , 2000 ,	wax	paper , tea bag , thread , indigo-dyed , pleated , sewn
130	versa as his metaphorical method supposedly advocates . Darwin	waxes	particularly lyrical in describing the flight of Montgolfier
131	forums for wheedling , intimidation , and braggadocio . He would	wax	pensive , once actually expressing a kind of remorse for not
132	along those lines . But do n't blame Sears for not	waxing	philosophical about handy Craftsman wrenches . # The author
133	his purple tracksuit pants and a dark blue bathrobe , is	waxing	philosophical about the gunfire rattling outside his window at
134	What do you think , Stephen - I mean , to	wax	philosophical here - of a situation like this , of which there
135	newspapers . Articles and editorials in Mexico City newspapers	waxed	poetic about the meanings and values of the upcoming Central
136	to triumph . " # In his own diaries , Guevara	waxed	poetic : " I see it printed in the night sky that
137	its marvels , however , it 's hard to imagine anyone	waxing	poetic about the stuff Bill Brown and Chip Searoans make . It
138	really deal under pressure- then they 're acting instead of just	waxing	poetic about freedom . They do it in Model UN and I
139	home for a visit after this stint .) He can	wax	poetic about opening his eyes after a nap , and drinking in
140	clan 's heritage . Maybe it 's an uncle who can	wax	poetic about the elders who migrated North , or the sisterin --
141	Theatre : Arrival One-2-One Bar : The Derailers The Parish :	Wax	Poodie 's : Bracken Hale , Tessy Lou & the Shotgun Stars
142	to end . " # Kresse , like others , can	wax	positively poetic about this time of year , about the " beauty
143	products . Cost Comparison # At 25 percent v/v , Johnson	Wax	Professional (Pro Strip) was found to be the cheapest product
144	was a Japanese American who enjoyed betting on the horses and	waxing	profound with traditional Oriental wisdom . Detective Hams ,
145	it and the phyllomedusine frogs of South America . Wiping and	waxing	provide the Indian frog with only modest water resistance , so
146	showdown by decking Vriska , after which Vriska begins to	wax	red for her . # Roxy punched Meenah in order to escape
147	polls , and as I say , she is going to	wax	Scott Brown 's pathetic ss SO BADLY in the debates and on

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148	most dangerous room with the most inadequate security . These	wax	seals and simple padlocks are hardly enough to keep deadly
149	. (Footage-of-man-wax) GEIST : (Voiceover) Duct Tape and	wax	seem to be the secrets to winning . Unidentified Man 9 :
150	usually the real basis of any project over which the Jew	waxes	sentimental ! 30 . How many Jews are there in the
151	a trace tech , Because I doubt any real CSI would	wax	so rhapsodic About that particular specialty . And , clearly ,
152	this , imagine the outcry should one of our politicians suddenly	wax	Socratic in the middle of a presidential debate : # " You
153	phonograph in fact was a rotating cylinder of tinfoil . (Wax	soon replaced foil as the more sensitive recording medium .) You
154	his demeanor . With his Far East project , he 's	waxing	statesmanlike . He 's modeling , perhaps , for a run to
155	Lotion and Epicurean Soap Sexy Shea Butter . Go wild with	waxing	Stencil kits are the latest way to shape the bikini area .
156	for his young readers never flags . And while he sometimes	waxes	stern when it comes to religious zealots and the proponents of
157	earned him the awe of his peers and the right to	wax	thanatological . " Death through exhaustion , " he surmises , "
158	" L " ll wax that ass ! L " ll	wax	that ass . - Lord have mercy , I " ll wax
159	where Jess has hidden two radio collars . // My group	waxes	the other . We find our collar - and theirs . Our
160	my money for my first guitar was dusting the pews and	waxing	the cross and shoveling the snow out in front of the church
161	of the motorhome ? # It 's Sparky , washing and	waxing	the roof ... Sparky insists that she is more surefooted than Eldy
162	tyre damage . What are you doing ? - I 'm	waxing	the floor . You know , it 's nice to know that
163	the damage ? I have to wash all our uniforms ,	wax	the X-Jet and clean out the Danger Room every day for a
164	Kellene , I need to know HOW to can butter ,	wax	the cheese and can meat . do you have an archive where
165	expeditions seemed to dissolve another dulling coat of paste	wax	the city had pressed upon Matthew . Gard encouraged his demands
166	medical problem . Baby , what 's wrong ? Did they	wax	the floor at Neiman 's again ? - I twisted my ankle
167	on your skis , you might as well go ahead and	wax	them . Waxing helps protect your ski bases , as well as
168	much as one and a half hours after sundown.17 The Moon	waxes	to first quarter at 3:31 P.M. EST.18 As the sky darkens ,
169	the house , she had soot to smear her face ,	wax	to black out one tooth . She would go about as a
170	paraffin treatment when necessary . " I also do the paraffin	wax	treatment for my hands , " Taylor says . " It leaves
171	be a better investment in the long run , compared to	waxing	treatments . # Laser hair removal treatments work best for
172	essentially a communal activity , " says Greeley , who regularly	waxes	warmly about his own experience growing up in a Chicago parish .
173	ads . It also gets rust off nails and hinges ,	waxes	your car perfectly ... - and weatherproofs windows . - Is n't
174	- And by end , I mean , I 'll be	waxing	your ass . Fuck you . I 'm not even letting you
175	you . Trees , lakes , animals , insects . Something	waxing	your butt there , Theodore ? Just not a big fan of
176	Wait a second ! Wait a second ! Hero ? !	Wax	! Hero ? ! Wax ! Her ... ? ! Wax heroes
177	Al uses one of these to buff his legs before he	waxes	em . Now , speaking of wax - for a gentler
178	, nails , massage (including Hot Rocks Massage) ,	waxing	(no body treatments) . Special : Hard-to-find European
179	cause microscopic wounds and irritations and burns (in case of	waxing) for microbes to prey on . # This can lead to
180	. Love is what ca n't be helped . When it	waxes	, and when it wanes . Love is what happens when you
181	room ? Ten lounge chairs , all services , facial ,	waxing	, manicure , we hold your hands . When I look around
182	. There are some who say that when the moon is	waxing	, she dares things not even Magda would try . # Now
183	no dishes , no 30-days grounded , no extra mowing ,	waxing	, painting , raking or scrubbing . Of course , his eyebrows
184	place , has never fully furnished it . The floors need	waxing	, and the pigeons on the air conditioner make a mess of
185	ink , though , it " prints " in plastic ,	wax	, resin , wood , concrete , gold , titanium , carbon

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186	Temple University Press , 1999. \$19.95 (paper) . #	Wax	, Murray L. Western rationality and the angel of dreams : Self
187	Had I fantasized about spanking ? Serious playing with clamps ,	wax	, et cetera ? Bondage ... rope ? Leather ? Rubber fetish
188	, Niger , early to mid-20th century Silver , glass ,	wax	, 8cm x 4.4cm x 0.5cm (3 ? x 1 3/4
189	, trimming may be the safest option . If you must	wax	, keep the following in mind . Get it done by a
190	sensitive and could sting from the products . * Do n't	wax	, get electrolysis or undergo laser hair removal if you 're
191	your brow hair too : plucking , threading , tweezing and	waxing	-- just find the way that suits you best and you 're
192	They switched mixtures . He already has a mustache . She	waxes	. # And then there is the endurance issue . Stewart says
193	. # It appears as a crescent when the moon is	waxing	. # It appears approximately two weeks after and before a new
194	# I am also quite impressed with your rooftop washing and	waxing	. Someone suggested wearing water shoes up there and I thought
195	. Stop moon . Wane not . I command thee .	Wax	. That 's it . That 's the man I love .
196	Oh , I 'm so real , I did n't even	wax	. Mo , get that bush out of here . And last
197	masculinity - an upper lip with a blond mustache impervious to	waxing	; thick patches of hair on her arms , legs , and
198	Ask a Woman : Do You Prefer a Man Who	Waxes	? # Answer : Ah yes , that is the question ,
199	no -- - GALAFANAKIS ! - Are n't you the 5:00	wax	? - That 's me . I 'm gon na kill you
200	. Wait , so what exactly wasTorres upset he could n't	wax	? I do n't know , McGee . He did n't get

Appendix 2

N+2			
Line	Left	Middle	Right
1	and Wax 1980 ; Wax 1982 , 1984 ; Cassell and	Wax	1981 . For critical analyses of the ethical systems of modern
2	. I think you can wax a ball . You can	wax	a ball . Wait , hang on . Does hair grown directly
3	find a new use , " says Tom . Tom Joyal	waxes	a circular jamb built in his workshop to mate two half-moon ,
4	make hair less noticeable so you 'll have to shave or	wax	about half as often . FICTION There 's no proof these creams
5	stay the course in a sluggish recovery than hear a politician	wax	about yet another grandiose agenda . # Second terms often have
6	When it comes to finding that special someone , Steve Lee	waxes	analytic : In 16 months , the Manhattan hedge-fund manager sped
7	and discover that " Mr. Allen " had hired someone to	wax	and buff their Hummers and Escalades . The wild spending
8	, dark fuzz that makes you miserable , temporary fixes like	waxing	and depilatories may not seem like enough , says Brandt . For
9	their talents through years of focusing solely on the art of	waxing	and nothing else . Going to anyone else
10	the Packard the sergeant loved , the Packard he liked to	wax	and polish to a shine ; but that was n't the only
11	let alone remains in , static equilibrium . Species continually	wax	and wane in relative abundance ; they even go extinct locally and
12	old styles still persist while other , smaller movements	wax	and wane , with Gehryism and Deconstructivism and virtual
13	it through my son 's first year , though it does	wax	and wane from day to day . It is hard to deal
14	after that first success , most writers ' imaginations seem to	wax	and wane at will despite the authors ' best efforts . "
15	are all that informative , since voter enthusiasm can	wax	and wane over the course of the cycle . # Our research
16	norm against blatant prejudice and discrimination --	waxed	and waned in particular situations and over past centuries . For
17	, the question of the naturalness of innocence has rather	waxed	and waned . The eighteenth century Romantics were of the view
18	William in the twenty-first century , but the family fortune had	waxed	and waned several times since then . Welly 's father would never
19	are weeds (Seymour 1969) . Their relative abundance has	waxed	and waned with two important landscape shifts over much of the
20	of how carbon dioxide concentrations in the atmosphere have	waxed	and waned with global temperatures in the last few million years
21	, as you know , in the Pacific Ocean . It	waxes	and wanes somewhat , it gets a little cooler . But it
22	# Executive orders in my mind is just one of those	waxing	and waning of power in the various branches . You cite executive
23	thought to conceive the two chief aspects of the moon (waxing	and waning moon) as twin deities , in which connection sometimes
24	identity was constantly renegotiated in a tumultuous age of	waxing	and waning political systems . # From their beginnings in north
25	dedicate his words to Ben Bernanke : # We have been	waxing	and wanning around the \$4 mark here in Northeastern Ohio . \$3.89
26	over the snow . Many products are available that make ski	waxing	as easy to do as waxing the car-wipe on , let dry
27	whole world was dying to be governess in that family .	Wax	candles in the schoolroom ! . You may imagine how desirable .
28	do with it ? ! I 'm thinking ... crayons ,	wax	candles , chariot wheels , wax ... You could always donate it
29	of which would be , # the love of many shall	wax	cold . This would be the case of many , but not
30	word without fear ; or as some read it , "	waxing	confident in the Lord " ; connecting the phrase , " in
31	residuals , egg shells , gypsum wallboard , broiler litter ,	wax	corrugated cardboard from poultry processing , soybean meal ,
32	a man responding to any gift vouchsafed him by Allah should	wax	covetous -- then will his gift slide apart as though it were
33	be on the water all day , and slathering on Wool	Wax	Creme in winter , a potion fishermen used to keep their hands
34	wildflowers is similar to that in the subalpine zone , but	wax	currant grows here instead of Colorado currant . Sidebar

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35	uncover a lost historiography . Any idea what that is ?	Wax	cylinder . From some old-school phonograph . Phonograph ... On
36	a report on historic audio recordings . Antique records and	wax	cyinders can be so fragile that they are damaged by the needle
37	insisted , softening his voice , as he always did when	waxing	dictatorial . " I 'm as surprised by the result as you
38	of the disc . What does n't fade away decays .	Wax	discs are frangible : a lost flake is an irretrievable snippet of
39	we 've all gone home . I trust my instincts ,	wax	doubtful or enthusiastic , grumble Englishly and liberally
40	wrought iron shelves held thousands of squat burning candles ,	wax	dripping like steady tears onto the floor . From a distance they
41	funny . That 's really funny . And if you start	waxing	drunk about that chick , I swear ... Do n't worry about
42	. Right ? # Phil , I so live when you	wax	ecstatic over scientific discoveries like this . Your post on
43	had a sort of Dr. Jack and Mr. Hyde persona ,	waxing	eloquent about human suffering one minute , proposing creepy
44	nature , beyond human control . # Similarly , commentators who	wax	eloquent about the ill effects of unwed motherhood on teenaged
45	cheerful and maudlin in a matter of minutes . He will	wax	eloquent about the freedom of living under a bridge - the fresh
46	. The show also includes audio recordings of family members	waxing	eloquent on their often-difficult journeys to Texas . They
47	, exaggerate the historical significance of revivalism , and	wax	eloquent over Prohibition . They tend to ignore or disparage the
48	zone it is in their home district , and suddenly just	wax	eloquently about a subject that nobody 's been talking about all
49	percent natural bees wax . MO ROCCA : Danielle Zanfardino	waxes	enthusiastic about the benefits of hair removal . She 's a waxing
50	speaks for the audience of his time and hers when she	waxes	enthusiastic over the way he brought the camera into
51	magazine titled " Incubator for New Voices , " and Kaplan	waxes	euphoric about the program 's virtues to anyone who 'll listen .
52	and smoked hand-rolled cigarettes . Andrew had begun to	wax	euphoric , as he cut into his pancakes , about the same
53	" meaning wax . Cerologist refers to the Waxing the City	waxing	experts who have refined their talents through years of
54	rich in this country , forget God and his people ,	wax	fat , and kick themselves out of the Church and go to
55	. The Presidents Gallery by Madame Tussauds is home to	wax	figures of all 44 U.S. Presidents and features interactive and
56	" What was that in the drawer ? " # "	Wax	for sealing envelopes . " # " In the other drawer .
57) With ragged fingernail he mined dirt , blood , and	wax	from his ear when he might have done better to leave it
58	. I ask him more about it , expecting him to	wax	geekish about its magic . But Swanson merely shrugs . " I
59	It flares it does-the civil strife-it wanes to a fingernail and	waxes	gibbous , it ravages the countryside , while back in Londinium
60	last quarter are the four primary phases . Waxing crescent ,	waxing	gibbous , waning gibbous , and waning crescent are the
61	boy ! - LANI : Stop it ! Come on ,	wax	head ! - Hey ! Hey ! - LANI : Stop it
62	day by day the fury swells aflame , And the woe	waxes	heavier day by day- Unless thou dost destroy even by new blows
63	month . Marry Gail . If she goes a week without	waxing	her moustache , they 'll think it 's Steve Harvey . MONTANA
64	did he do ? Make fun of her ? Helped her	wax	her moustache . She has a moustache ? Not anymore . Supposedly
65	s regal . It 's very Prince William . Does he	wax	his balls too ? Can you wax a ball ? Mmm !
66	, woperson , or chairperdaughter ever seencritics still	wax	hysterical over language changes . It 's the same old bottle ,
67	box where your head is kept , resist the urge to	wax	ignorant on her naughty bits . " # " I do n't
68	amid all this , the Anti-Defamation League feels the need to	wax	indignant over a few lines on a Web log ? " #
69	the documentary " Maiden , " and the author Toni Morrison	waxes	irreverent in another documentary , " The Pieces I Am . "
70	at the Juicy Fruit or Coca-Cola , then buy yot or	wax	lips for something sweet . Only the Americans and their whores
71	4th , and then on the 5th and 6th an ultraslender	waxing	lunar crescent makes its climb past the three wonderful evening
72	having it . So as I gloss over my penny-pinching by	waxing	lyrical about abysmal stipends and the GINI coefficient , the
73	Act Like an Insider , Think Like an Outsider Management gurus	wax	lyrical about being inventive and " thinking out of the box .

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74	we can not properly foresee . I wish I could just	wax	lyrical about some of the developments we can at least sensibly
75	read in Bioethics is just doctors and other do-gooders trying to	wax	lyrical about their good intentions . Goodness and truth can
76	and indeed , they may have been drawn after clay or	wax	models . In the drawing these heroic nudes conform to the concave
77	puts you in the same category as those Americans who "	wax	moralistic " against the Israelis . Except , you wax moralistic
78	, and the cylinders were initially called New High Speed Hard	Wax	Moulded Records until the name was changed to Gold Moulded . By
79	store , and even the gas station , grocery market and	wax	museum . # Today , residents who want to buy a bottle
80	teaching experience through a social studies wax museum . #	Wax	museums foster a positive collaborative experience between
81	get more excited over other people 's triumphs than my own	wax	my car , slowly , with a bikini . # Article copyright
82	had people voting on me ... I would n't employ to	wax	my car . And yet I go before the great tenure committee
83	LATER ON -- STICK AROUND -- I 'M GON NA	WAX	MY LEGS . UNH-UNH . THAT HURTS . WHY CA N'T YOUR
84	cover along with bulrushes , spikerushes , and other sedges .	Wax	myrtle is the most common shrub , but bladderpod thrives in
85	patches of saw grass , St. John 's wort , and	wax	myrtle . Wildlife is somewhat sparse because of the poor soil ,
86	back on the same beach with children of their own ,	waxing	nostalgic about a place where , no matter your choice of lodging
87	for an earlier , more innocent America . But instead of	waxing	nostalgic about the 1950s , as did Reagan-era Republicans ,
88	publishers . But nineteenth-century , literati continued to	wax	nostalgic for bardic poets , scribal arts , and noble patrons .
89	the spirit-summer camp ! # Who 'd have thought I 'd	wax	nostalgic for wieners ? Or s'mores ? Or bug juice , toxic
90	A DAY from trip 's end . Already , I 'm	waxing	nostalgic , trying to stretch and deepen every moment . I grab
91	farmhouse , Matt Millen peers into the lone unfinished room and	waxes	nostalgic . He spent nearly 9 years restoring the
92	they spend most of the time blocked . But with ear	wax	not blood , blood would be way more impressive and with wax
93	hail thou dawn . # Her voice and dance , now	waxing	now waning , were a nascent smile of joy . She now
94	kinda knows what he 's talking about . Wax on ,	wax	off type of [Bleep] . Italian style . High , high ,
95	. Hey , guys ! Check this ! Wax on .	Wax	off . - Wax on ... - Mouth off ! - Hey
96	Ralph Macchio ? Yes , Pat Morita . Wax on .	Wax	off . Yeah , " paint the fence , " yeah .
97	branch thereof will not cease. Though the root thereof	wax	old in theearth , and the stock thereof die in the ground
98	we observe what 's lost at any time , When things	wax	old with eld and foul decay , Or when salt seas eat
99	hell would not have been sitting in Baton Rouge watching LSU	wax	Ole Miss that , which is what I told an LSU student
100	Print book lovers (I 'm one of ' em)	wax	on about their beloved format 's special talents : the smell ,
101	until of course they 're fixed , when we can all	wax	on about how wonderful Microsoft is for making us happy . It
102	(COLOR) : Red Grove , 1994 , oil and	wax	on panel , 48 x 24 . Courtesy Phyllis Well & Company
103	5-June 12 . " Salvador Dal , " a retrospective ,	wax	on view at the Salvador Dal Museum , St. Petersburg Sept. 12
104	of . # SERENDIPITY # How so ? # METATRON #	Wax	on , wax off . (points OC) The Woman rolls
105	adding : " If she wants her nails done , or	waxing	or a facial , Elizabeth Arden Red Door . They have these
106	n't care and do bad work . Stay with tweezing ,	waxing	or lotions instead . # Electrologists try to discourage
107	another detail who ca n't decide if it 's better to	wax	or shave to get the bald look . The contractors are mostly
108	washed and waxed my glamorous aunt 's linoleum to wash and	wax	our crumbling kitchen floor once every two weeks . We had to
109	s okay . It 's okay . - We were just	waxing	our legs . - Off ? For your information this happens to
110	area is a great place for a dispenser for aluminum ,	wax	paper and plastic wrap . - And what about my special drawer
111	Compass , bug spray , water , knife , trowel ,	wax	paper , a basket , a cooler with ice , and Chardonnay.

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112	DIGGINS (United States) -Indigo Bark Group , 2000 ,	wax	paper , tea bag , thread , indigo-dyed , pleated , sewn
113	minutes . Remove cake from pan and place on parchment or	wax	paper . Let stand for 2 hours before serving . # Prepare
114	remarkably strong nerves . When questioned , Italian experts	wax	patriotic and point out that things always have gone quite well
115	Franklin say ? ' # Ron Avery is n't going to	wax	philosophic about freedom : " He would say ' Set the record
116	link . It 's a great read , as Schmidt also	waxed	poetic about self-driving cars -- which are being developed by
117	assignment for my students . # Reviewing the syllabus , I	waxed	poetic about the readings we 'd be doing and how they exemplify
118	# freely : " In fact , all of you folks	waxing	poetic about the SFH on a 1/4th of an acre with mass
119	really deal under pressure- then they 're acting instead of just	waxing	poetic about freedom . They do it in Model UN and I
120	to " channel the primitive woman " she has learned to	wax	poetic about the " casual way in which nature treats life and
121	The point of this post is not , however , to	wax	poetic about my political choices or about your duty to vote (
122	set , DJ Ronnie Fox is told by KXLA FM to	wax	poetic on the topic . Ronnie 's played this game before .
123	think it would be hard to work alone . " Stan	waxes	poetic , quoting James Thurber : " He bold as an eagle
124	1994 , Bono , of the Irish rock group U2 ,	waxed	poetic : " Rock-and -- roll people love Frank Sinatra because
125	, commonly called pagne , are of two main types :	wax	prints and roller prints (also simply referred to as " wax
126	as alternatives to solvent-based products such as Johnson	Wax	Professional (Pro Strip) . The authors applied a quick
127	and others where it is worn almost as jewelry . Guidebooks	wax	prosaic about ancient sex orgies in the villa of Tiberius (as
128	it and the phyllomedusine frogs of South America . Wiping and	waxing	provide the Indian frog with only modest water resistance , so
129	book Silk Painting -- The Artist 's Guide to Gutta and	Wax	Resist Techniques . Moyer is conducting a series of
130	weapons . The finger-pointers of five minutes ago suddenly	wax	righteous in their indignation that mere expression -- rather ,
131	, which set alight a self-sustaining , self-replicating ,	waxing	roar that rose for a half-hour and tumbled from the stadium on
132	. I called him the other day , expecting him to	wax	sentimental about the blue haze and perfume of a smoky bar in
133	broadcast next season , that is ... # Yaggi could only	wax	sentimental at the loss of that power-packed NFC lineup (
134	the family , when Hallie was in first grade , and	waxing	skeptical where such things as sleigh-driving saints , elves
135	, had participated in the same revelries about which Joey was	waxing	so nostalgic , and Sateesh , Martha 's husband , had heard
136	the Rclame Conference Series in November 1999 , at the Thread	Waxing	Space in New York , on a panel organized by Judith Rodenbeck
137	9163 Burn ! White flame of new light , #	wax	stronger daily , energizing the earth with your glow . # Turn
138	be alone with my woman sometimes ... damn near ready to	wax	that ass ... and all I can do is vision this fool
139	for sale to outsiders . People are also modeling clay or	wax	that ends up as a terracotta sculpture (say , Nok or
140	. P104 Joleb was there . His hair coated by Butch	Wax	that made him look like a scared bear with a crush on
141	? That 's none of your business . You need to	wax	that , sweetie . Hair down there 's not an option for
142	store , " " lay down the mulch , wash and	wax	the car , get the kids at school , " " rent
143	keeping that pesky body hair in check . # Welcome to	Waxing	the City ... we look forward to meeting you ! # Cerologist
144	expeditions seemed to dissolve another dulling coat of paste	wax	the city had pressed upon Matthew . Gard encouraged his demands
145	one duty chance . Clarence ! I ca n't have you	waxing	the customers . You want a big job ? Okay . I
146	constitutes negligence . " # " What 's so wrong about	waxing	the floors ? " the Browns replied . " Why should we
147	the south side of the building was closed , something about	waxing	the hallways . " We just want to peek in , "
148	even tell you how to adjust your kick zone or correctly	wax	the ski . Of course , when you 're out in nature
149	not hot (test it on your inner wrist) .	Wax	the upper areas that border your shape as well as your inner

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150	. Vlad had read somewhere that the Muslim habit of men	waxing	their bodies had entered Europe through Arab-Hispanic culture
151	stop at some secluded spot along the Five Mile Drive to	wax	their cars . I had n't thought of it until that second
152	and W under their belt against Albany on November 11 ,	waxing	them 82-60 . Ohio State came out very rusty in that game
153	much as one and a half hours after sundown.17 The Moon	waxes	to first quarter at 3:31 P.M. EST.18 As the sky darkens ,
154	sits about 3 degrees to the Moon 's left.19 The Moon	waxes	to first quarter at 1:27 p.m . EDT.20 At 7:02 a.m .
155	8126 2 The Moon	waxes	to first quarter at 7:11 a.m. eastern daylight time (EDT)
156	and John McCain . Flag burning remains unsafe and legal ,	wax	with Syria looks unlikely , and as Joe Scarborough recently
157	and external portion of the auditory canal of all accretions and	wax	with the aid of a cotton swab . This will allow intimate
158	. I alone am inactive and reveal no signs , And	wax	without having reached the limit . Like a baby that has not
159	earlier clarion call . Ivins , 59 , as always ,	waxes	witty and wise ; for instance : " Bush had two voluntary
160	egg . Mealworms or silk worms , or rarely crickets and	wax	worms are also an important treat to the hedgehog 's diet which
161	Ina boat ramp ; bluegill good using crickets , worms ,	wax	worms , meal worms and small jigs in the back of necks
162	A six-pack of Schmidt and some bait . - Shiners or	wax	worms ? - I ca n't afford shiners , give me the
163	transgressions . And has resulted in a self-flagellation that	waxes	worse and worse as time progresses . # News flash : All
165	is if you get a bikini wax . And they	wax	you and then they show it to you , and there is
166	Woman 5 : Strip waxing your chest ? RIVERA : Strip	waxing	your chest . Ms-ANDERSON : Waxing -- waxing your chest .
167	when you go to court . UNIDENTIFIED-MALE# You need to	wax	your eyebrows . WATTERS# Could you do that for me in the
168	both Agatha Paris . 22 GROOM LIKE A GUY Instead of	waxing	your lip , just shave it . That 's right : Unless
169	brains and struggle through the hard stuff of life instead of	waxing	your pride on a website about failure . It serves you no
170	All right ? I 'll go . Just go upstairs and	wax	your skis or your legs or whatever you wax . All right
171	with color inside her wimple . " Why are n't you	waxing	your string for the Cheerio contest ? " she said . #
172	Zani , a Denver aesthetician , says " resins are just	waxes	" - although the base extract is from trees . She more
173	but not elsewhere on the face . Cost is comparable to	waxing	(\$ 20 for half-leg or bikini area ; \$ 10 for
174) -Untitled , 1999 , wood , dye , metal ,	wax	, 29 x 16 x 26 inches , in " 33.32.02 :
175) . Hair-Removal Heroes These new products can make shaving ,	waxing	, and even electrolysis go a lot more smoothly * DREAM CREAM
176	he 'd gotten from the Pontiac dealer , and washing ,	waxing	, and buffing the exterior . He 'd neglected the mechanical side
177	, smoking . The rocks near Woods Hole had turned to	wax	, caked in white sea ice . Flocks of ducks bobbed through
178	why you need to diligently apply them daily after shaving or	waxing	, explains Richard Maksimowski , director of skincare product
179	to help your postop appearance : * Do all tweezing ,	waxing	, facials and hair coloring presurgery. * Always wear sun
180	, trimming may be the safest option . If you must	wax	, keep the following in mind . Get it done by a
181	for you . If you plan to do a lot of	waxing	, or if you 're setting up shop in an unventilated basement
182	Femininity is ' perfected ' by the addition of make-up ,	waxing	, plucking , hair-styles and clothes and codes of appropriate '
183	children check their work . Repeat for the words rack ,	wax	, sack , and the sentence Matt sat . (Teacher 's
184	SO MUCH # Anything that disrupts the skin (acne ,	waxing	, shaving or a mosquito bite) causes inflammation , which often
185	in which she held forth on such gender-specific topics as leg	waxing	, stretch marks and PMS . But for Jones , one contemporary
186	live As mortals by eternal give and take . The nations	wax	, the nations wane away ; In a brief space the generations
187	improvised a device from things in the clinic : bottles ,	wax	, tubes . The man , his expression blank , sat bolt
188	exhibition , Feb. 1-24) -Foil , 2000 , steel ,	wax	, vessel 45 by 48 inches , runner 81 by 42 by
189	have to wax or shave the growing stubble . Also ,	waxing	, which some find quite painful , can cause rashes , burns

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190	The Other Machine Co. ' s signature tool mills plastic ,	wax	, wood , and metals into precise 3-D models . It can
191	little miracles , little votive objects , made of silver ,	wax	, wood and so forth , which show a -- certain parts
192	of a multitude of yesteryears he could not place . "	Wax	, " she repeated helpfully . She had a pretty smile ,
193	. (Acorn caps , \$2.50 for 100 ; kringlescountrystore.com .	Wax	, \$6.70 for 11/2 pounds ; wicks , \$2.99 for 10 yards
194	threading convert . # First , it 's way cheaper than	waxing	. Instead of \$32 I was used to paying , it was
195	a minute . I have a girl that does a bikini	wax	. Now ! Oh , all right . Bucking for a raise
196	, work by removing hair at the root , similar to	waxing	. This produces much longer-lasting results . When hair grows
197	result as well as your next choice would be depilatories or	waxing	. Though waxing is better than shaving , you have to be
198	. - I got money , nigga . Shut up ,	Wax	. - Fifty dollars , you can have this . Oh ,
199	# you 'd go blind ... your body would turn to	wax	... they 'd have to put you in a wheelbarrow and ...
200	what I want to be , " says Kate , intently	waxing	: " a scientist . " # " Clay Boats , "